

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADVERTISING IN BUSINESS TOURISM AND NATIONAL CULTURAL ACTIVITY IN MANAGEMENT

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Annotation: The author conducts a sociocultural analysis of tourism management in Uzbekistan based on the existing tourism management of European tourism management. In the following pages of article devoted to the strategic and structural development of tourism and its opportunities in the country. The following article describes the importance of the role of advertising in business tourism and provides a structural, linguistic analysis of the advertising text and highlights its strategic aspects. Based on the scientific research of world linguists, there are given clear ideas about the rules of advertising and the writing of parts of advertising.

Key words: tourist, tourism, recreational, ecotourism, agro tourism, gap-year, religious, educational, cultural, adventure, winter, sport tourism, advertising, target audience, product concept; media, reference strategy, title, visual aids, columns, body text, headlines, inserts, frames, slogans, logos, facts, notes.

Аннотация: Автор проводит социокультурный анализ туристического менеджмента в Узбекистане на основе существующего туристического менеджмента европейского туристического менеджмента. В следующих страницах статьи, посвященной стратегическому и структурному развитию туризма и его возможностей в стране. В статье проводится роль рекламы в бизнеса туризм и структурный лингвистический анализ рекламного текста и освещаются его стратегические аспекты. На основании научных исследований мировых лингвистов существуют четкие представления о правилах рекламы и написании частей рекламного текста.

Ключевые слова: турист, туризм, региональный, эко туризм, агро туризм, командировочный и летный, религиозный, образовательный, культурный, приключение, зимний, спортивный туризм, реклама, целевая аудитория, концепция продукта; медиа, справочная стратегия, заголовок, визуальные медиа, столбцы, основной текст, заголовки, вставки, рамки, слоганы, логотипы, факты, примечания.

Tourism is a factor that accelerates the process of economic development and plays an important role in solving economic and social problems. The role of

tourism in creating additional jobs, increasing employment, and improving the country's well-being is incomparable.

In the tourist services provided in the Republic of Uzbekistan the characteristics of the distribution of functions are as follows: All trips, whether in domestic or international tourism, are evaluated as organized and unorganized. It is an organized type of travel abroad or in one's own country with the help of tourist companies. An unorganized tour is a trip organized by tourists to their own country or abroad, alone or in a group. Usually, this category of tourism is referred to as "amateur tourism" (commonly known as "wild people"). [Kotler P., Bowen J. & Mackens J., 2014].

Special statistics of organized and unorganized tours are not conducted on a national and international scale, but according to experts, organized tourism accounts for about 35% of the total volume of world tourism, and unorganized tourism accounts for about 65%. Although the percentage of organized species is still far behind that of unorganized species, in absolute numbers organized species are more numerous streams and is increasing year by year. Tourist firms are understood to be business entities, engaged in intermediary operations on a commercial basis in the field of tourism services.

Advertising is very important in tourism. Modern man is present in all spheres of the social sphere in the discursive practices of advertising speech - objective reasons: the reality of social commercialization, the development of mass media and the emergence of new types of mass media, interactive, social awareness of consumption and many other things for others occupies one of the positions as a strict consumer. [Bolotnova N.S. 2006], As a result, scientists in various fields of knowledge began to analyze the advertising text as a form of communication. In the scientific literature [B.G. Matveev, 1987.] there are many definitions of advertising. Thus, according to various authors, advertising: It is the cheapest way to find a buyer for a product or service; Creating and distributing the image of the product and service, thus making the consumer want to buy it; The way to successfully sell something; increasing the demand for goods and services by attracting the consumer's attention to them; A means of persuasive information about goods, services or benefits, preparing potential buyers for purchase, commercial propaganda about the consumer characteristics of goods, services.

In the scientific literature, 5 goals of good writing are highlighted:

a) Attention is the first goal. The main element here is the title. Medium: illustration. Important features: color, size, unusual sound, video... b) Interest - attention is not enough, that is, it is necessary to be interesting to keep this attention. The target of advertising is the consumer. s) Trust - people need to trust. They only read what interests them. Modern humans have certainly become more complex. d) Desire- In order to arouse desire, it is necessary to talk about the benefits of the product. For this, it is necessary to know the buyer well. It is necessary to know clearly about the benefit of the product. Immediate action or future action is a factor that is often overlooked in many ads, such as the fact that people are not interested in your product, and that their work is too much for them.

It is known that advertising or creative strategy consists of four elements: 1) target audience; 2) product concept; 3) means of information distribution; 4) as an appeal strategy. First of all, let's define the appeal strategy. What is an appeal strategy? It is determined by what and how the company wants to communicate? The task of disseminating this idea includes the task of developing a simple, interesting, informative, entertaining, enjoyable, useful, verbal and non-verbal way to visualize this expression. In order to write the advertising text correctly, it is necessary to develop an appeal strategy first. The communication strategy consists of three operational elements: 1. Textual basis - what and how do you want to convey? 2. The artistic part - what and how do you want to show? 3. Technical tools - what and how do you want to create with technical tools? To develop these elements, the copywriter and the artist need to analyze the research results and facts, study the market, the product and the competition.

Next, if we pay attention to the text, the text should express in writing the most important aspects that should be reflected in the main advertisement or during the campaign, that is, it is necessary to know the answer to the question of who the potential buyer can be. Focusing on non-verbal means such as artistic decoration and technical execution during the composition of the text is the next process. In this case, all three parts of it are important: text space, artistic decoration and technical performance. They are developed in harmony with each other. A complete description of the elements of the communication strategy is the most important prerequisite for creative development, which is considered the core of an advertising ad or campaign. It is the strategy that ensures that the advertisement says what it needs to say, to whom it needs to be said, and in what tone it is needed.

As given in the literature on this field, [Medvedeva E.V., 2003.] the first stage of creating an advertising text is the stage of "Promotional development", which is both the most serious and the most productive. This is a long, tedious, difficult task of summarizing all the necessary information on the problems of choosing and analyzing a single verbal (word) or visual (image) concept to convey the necessary information. This means creating a visual representation of an advertising ad or banner until the text is written or the artistic look of the ad is created. This process can be called visualization or conceptualization, and it is an important step in advertising advertising. John Carey, the father of copywriting, believed that ideas are the most important thing in copywriting. According to him, there are 12 tested ways to find an advertising idea:- using one's personal experience;- analyzing one's own experience;- writing from the heart;- learning from the experience of others;- communicating with the manufacturer;- studying the product;- studying the previous advertisement about this product;- studying the advertisement of the competing product;- studying the testimonials of buyers;- solving the problems faced by prospective buyers;- putting all the intelligence to work;- returning the successful advertisement with minor changes, etc. All advertising texts consist of many elements or components. [Orlova O.V. 2006]. These elements can be mixed, exaggerated, reduced, swapped, changed or removed until something unique is created. The most important elements of a print advertisement; title, visual aids, columns, main text, headings, inserts (inserts), frames, slogans, logos, facts, notes. The headline is the most important element of a print ad. It is in the first place. Therefore, the title should be noticeable and attention-grabbing. The title is typed in capital letters. The title performs 6 main functions: 1) it needs to attract attention; 2) he should be able to choose his student (consumer of goods); 3) the title should direct the person to a certain thing, such as the reader to the main text; 4) commercial idea should be fully reflected in it; 5) the title should promise that you will benefit from the purchase of the goods; 6) it is necessary to reflect the novelty of the product that interests the reader in the title.

According to statistics on the Internet, [www.koob.ru.] experts estimate that people read the headline 5 times more than the text of the advertisement. So much depends on the title. There are many types of titles. Headings can be divided into 5 main types: 1) interesting - arouses interest in the reader, makes him want to know more and read the text. 2) informational type - here new information is given and "how to do it" (know, buy, etc.) is told. 3) interrogative -

widely used, but there is a risk of abuse of this method. If the reader finds an easy or negative answer to the question, then the likelihood of him reading the ad text decreases. 4) direct reference to the useful properties of the product is a direct reference to the useful properties of the product. 5) command tone - commands to do something. It's not always bad. Here's an example: "Promise your girlfriend anything you want, but give her Dolice (chocolate)!" [Medvedeva E.V., 2003.]

As a result, headlines serve to amplify the most important commercial point. It is necessary to take into account that the student does not want to study anymore. Here, what the title says is developed. The most important content of the information - numbers, facts - can be reflected in the headings. The main text covers all the information. Content should be in a commercial spirit and should be written in small print. 5 requirements for the main text: It is necessary to emphasize the main idea; It is necessary to clearly indicate the position of the goods; It should be emphasized to consumers that it is useful; The name of the trademark is highlighted and strengthened; The text is written clearly and concisely. The headline of the ad "a good headline is 75 percent of the success of an ad, because it grabs attention, so people read the ad. The title should be short (max. 7-8 words) effective and stand out like a slogan.

In this case, a different style or other original genre can be used in the structural construction of the advertisement. The text consists of 4 main elements: Introduction paragraph; Internal paragraphs; Intermediate code; Like code.

The introductory paragraph turns the reader's interest on the product; Internal paragraphs increase interest in the product, for this, the advertisement must be truthful and inspire confidence. Interval refers to the filling of the desire to order between paragraphs. A good ad copy has several such methods. Code - at the end of the ad, the appeal to the consumer is described, and it is told how to do it. This place in the advertisement is, literally, the point where the product is sold. The code may be direct or indirect in the form of an implicit suggestion or command. Inset and frames... slogans... seal, logos and signatures.

In conclusion, advertising should be written in a way that is clear, concise, interesting, persuasive, exciting, elegant and memorable. General statements do not convince anyone. Consumers need accurate information.

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